

CREDIT AND COLLECTION PRACTICES OF SELECTED SAVINGS BANKS IN CEBU: BASES FOR IMPROVEMENT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10686360>

Abstract

This study described the extent to which the credit practices are implemented by savings banks and the extent to which their collection practices are implemented and looked into the differences on how managerial personnel and the rank-and-file employees evaluated the implementation of their credit and collection practices. This study also made proposals that could improve the credit and collection practices of the selected savings banks in Cebu. Descriptive-survey research design was used with the questionnaire as primary tool for data collection. The Credit Practices and Collection Practices Questionnaire were given to 110 personnel composed of 37 managerial and 73 rank and file employees from the selected Savings Banks in Cebu as respondents of the study. These questionnaires were validated before these were distributed to the respondents. Weighted mean and t-test were used to analyzed and interpret the data. The study revealed that majority of the credit practices as well as the collection practices were implemented by the Savings Banks in Cebu to a Great Extent. However, there were also other measures which were implemented to a Moderate Extent and such practices should be addressed in order to improve their lending operations. It was found that there were no significant differences between the perceptions of the respondents belonging to the managerial personnel and rank and file employees on the extent of implementation of credit practices and the extent of implementation of collection practices of selected Savings Banks in Cebu.

Keywords: *Credit Practices, Collection Practices, Managerial Personnel, Rank and File Employees, Savings Bank*

INTRODUCTION

It cannot be denied that financial institutions are now facing problems to include non-performing loans and slow collection of receivables that can eventually result to closures or bankruptcies. For as long as there is credit or lending operations, delinquency or occurrence of past due will always be a problem. This requires appropriate credit evaluation measures and collection systems.

According to Bommarito (2012), failures of financial institutions, more specifically, banks were caused by factors that include 1) financial problems; 2) problematic credits; 3) imbalance of assets versus loans; 4) non-compliance of government regulations; 5) risk management decisions; 6) non-banking ventures; and 7) other reasons.

In fact, Tamba (2017) reported bank closures made by the BSP and put into receivership by the Philippine Deposit Insurance Corporation (PDIC). In the year 2015, a total of fourteen (14) rural banks were closed. For the year 2016, there were twenty-two (22) banks which were also closed down. Also, for year 2017, seven (7) banks were closed of which six (6) were rural banks and one (1) was a thrift or savings bank.

In addition, Douglas, Lont, and Scott (2014) cited that in the New Zealand, thirty-one (31) financing companies were closed from the years 2006 up to 2009. This resulted to some questions on the reasons for such failures. It was revealed that there were factors that contributed to such closures to include the deteriorating quality of assets caused by past due loans.

Moreover, Douglas, Lont, and Scott (2014) stressed that in order to prevent or if not minimize the problems of high past due loans, there is a need for financial institutions to strictly adopt the criteria of using the 5 or 6C's for the granting of loans and also implement certain collection systems for the recovery of loans receivables that ensures profitability and sustainability of business operations.

Although several researches have explored on how to improve the credit and collection practices of savings banks, this study looked on credit investigation and/or background investigation or gathering information on personal habits of prospective borrowers. Other intervention schemes were explored for implementation of savings banks.

Effective credit and collection practices are crucial for the financial stability and success of savings banks. In the context of Cebu, the practices of selected savings banks in managing credit and collections play a significant role in their overall performance and sustainability. The researchers believed that poor credit and collection practices can lead to increased non-performing loans and financial losses for banks. Therefore, understanding the current practices of savings banks in Cebu and identifying areas for improvement is essential for enhancing their operational efficiency and profitability. Hence, this study looks into some alternatives and endorse measures for the improvement of financial institutions, more particularly Savings or Thrift Banks.

Research Questions

This study has the main objective of determining the extent of implementing the credit and collection practices of selected savings banks in Cebu. More particularly, the study aimed to address the questions, as follows:

1. As evaluated by the respondents, what is the extent to which the credit practices are implemented by savings banks in terms of:
 - 1.1. Character;
 - 1.2. Capacity;
 - 1.3. Cash Flow;
 - 1.4. Collateral;
 - 1.5. Conditions; and
 - 1.6. Control?
2. As assessed by the respondents, what is the extent to which the collection practices are implemented by savings banks in terms of:
 - 2.1. Documentation;
 - 2.2. Manpower; and
 - 2.3. Procedures?
3. Are there significant differences between the evaluation of the managerial personnel and the rank and file employees regarding the extent to which credit and collection practices are implemented?
4. Based on the findings of the study, what proposals could be made to improve the credit and collection practices of the selected savings banks in Cebu?

METHODOLOGY

The researcher utilized the descriptive-survey research design in the conduct of this endeavor. In the collection of data, the questionnaire was utilized for the selected savings banks in determining the extent of implementing their credit and collection practices. Interviews were also conducted for additional information and clarifications from the respondents.

There were two groups of respondents in this study. The first group was composed of Managerial personnel (i.e., Branch Managers, Branch Heads, Supervisors) and the second group was the rank and file (i. e., non-managerial) employees most specially those involved in the credit and collection operations from the financial institutions in their area of coverage and were selected by purposive sampling from among the rank-and-file population. The respondents were given questionnaires for them to provide information intended for the study.

This study utilized the questionnaire as an instrument on the collection of data. The questionnaires were submitted to the panel during the proposal hearing for review and improvement. Then a dry-run was conducted to test its validity. It was answered by personnel who were not included in the official list of respondents. Before the study proper, the researcher wrote the Branch Managers of respective banks asking permission to distribute the questionnaires. These were composed of two (2) parts and every part of the instrument was accomplished by the Managerial Personnel and the rank-and-file

employees of the selected Savings Banks in Cebu. Each of the questionnaire was described here.

The Credit Practices Questionnaire. This questionnaire was used for evaluating the extent of credit practices of selected Savings Banks before granting loans to their clients. The questionnaire contains six questions. Every question contains a series of items. Related on every item comprised the scales and range with interpretation as presented below:

Scale	Range	Qualitative Description	Interpretation
4	3.26- 4.00	Great Extent (GE)	means that the credit practice is <u>implemented all the time.</u>
3	2.51- 3.25	Moderate Extent (ME)	implies that the credit practice is <u>implemented most of the time.</u>
2	1.76- 2.50	Less Extent (LE)	means that the credit practice is <u>sometimes implemented.</u>
1	1.00- 1.75	Never (N)	implies that the credit practice is <u>not implemented.</u>

The Collection Practices Questionnaire. This questionnaire was used for evaluating the extent of implementation of collection practices of selected Savings Banks. The questionnaire contains three questions. Every question contains a series of items. Related on every item comprised the scales and range with interpretation as presented below:

Scale	Range	Qualitative Description	Interpretation
4	3.26- 4.00	Great Extent (GE)	means that the credit practice is <u>implemented all the time.</u>
3	2.51- 3.25	Moderate Extent (ME)	implies that the credit practice is <u>implemented most of the time.</u>
2	1.76- 2.50	Less Extent (LE)	means that the credit practice is <u>sometimes implemented.</u>
1	1.00- 1.75	Never (N)	implies that the credit practice is <u>not implemented.</u>

The researcher had made instructions to the respondents by encircling the number that corresponds to their answer on every question.

Weighted mean was used to describe the extent to which the credit and collection practices are implemented by savings banks. Two sample t-test was used to determine whether or not there were significant differences between the perceptions of the respondents belonging to the managerial personnel and rank and file employees on the extent of implementation of credit practices and the extent of implementation of collection

practices of selected Savings Banks in Cebu. The difference was tested at .05 level of significance.

RESULTS

The extent of implementation of credit practices in terms of character is shown in Table 1.

Table 1

The Extent of Implementation of Credit Practices in terms of Character

Indicators	Managerial Personnel n =37		Rank and File Employees n =73		Item Average	
	μ	Scale	μ	Scale	μ	Scale
1) Securing information and knowing the reputation of potential borrowers among social, business friends, associates, and other financial institutions	3.86	GE	3.78	GE	3.82	GE
2) Updating the past payment record of the borrower, if he/she is an old client of the company	3.83	GE	3.68	GE	3.76	GE
3) Considering the experience of other lenders with availments of the prospective borrower	3.50	GE	3.24	ME	3.37	GE
4) Determining the borrower's ability in projecting potential cash flow or sources of revenue	3.67	GE	3.58	GE	3.63	GE
5) Calculating the rating of the potential client	3.86	GE	3.69	GE	3.78	GE
6) Considering the availability of guarantors or co-makers of the proposed loan	3.47	GE	3.24	ME	3.36	GE
7)Gathering information on personal habits such as gambling, drinking, church involvement, and civic activities	2.89	ME	2.74	ME	2.82	ME
8) Securing the payment record of the client from other financial institutions	3.31	GE	3.10	ME	3.21	ME
9) Sending and retrieving CI/BI form with other financial institutions such as banks and lending companies	3.25	ME	3.07	ME	3.16	ME

Factor Average	3.52	GE	3.35	GE	3.44	GE
1.00 – 1.75 Never (N)	1.76 – 2.50 Less Extent (LE)					
2.51 – 3.25 Moderate Extent (ME)	3.26 – 4.00 Great Extent (GE)					

The extent of implementation of credit practices in terms of capacity is shown in Table 2.

Table 2

The Extent of Implementation of Credit Practices in terms of Capacity

Indicators	Managerial Personnel n= 37		Rank and File Employees n =73		Item Average	
	μ	Scale	μ	Scale	μ	Scale
1) Determining the sources of income of the prospective borrower	3.94	GE	3.89	GE	3.92	GE
2) Securing information on employment and/or business involvement of the potential borrower	3.92	GE	3.86	GE	3.89	GE
3) Considering the age of the borrower to determine the legal capacity to enter into contract	3.92	GE	3.83	GE	3.88	GE
4) Ascertaining the marital status of client to ensure possible assistance in the payment of obligations	3.36	GE	3.24	ME	3.30	GE
5) Considering the identity of the potential borrower and his/her guarantors or co-makers	3.44	GE	3.29	GE	3.37	GE
6) Requiring at least two (2) guarantors or co-makers especially for non-collateralized loans	3.03	ME	3.07	ME	3.05	ME
7) Requiring copies of corporate by-laws and articles of incorporation, partnership agreements, and other legal documents	3.51	GE	3.33	GE	3.42	GE
8) Requiring the historical background, structure, owners or stockholders, and services in the industry	3.60	GE	3.35	GE	3.48	GE
Factor Average	3.59	GE	3.48	GE	3.54	GE

1.00 – 1.75 Never (N)
2.51 – 3.25 Moderate Extent (ME)

1.76 – 2.50 Less Extent (LE)
3.26 – 4.00 Great Extent (GE)

The extent of implementation of credit practices in terms of cash flow is shown in Table 3.

Table 3

The Extent of Implementation of Credit Practices in terms of Cash Flow

Indicators	Managerial Personnel n = 37		Rank and File Employees n = 73		Item Average	
	μ	Scale	μ	Scale	μ	Scale
1) Considering the take home pay or overall income of the individual borrower and the past earnings, dividends, and sales record in the case of a business firm or entity	3.86	GE	3.76	GE	3.81	GE
2) Determining the adequacy of past and projected cash flow of the client or borrower	3.77	GE	3.64	GE	3.71	GE
3) Considering the presence of liquid reserves of the potential client	3.54	GE	3.25	ME	3.40	GE
4) Determining the turnover of accounts receivables, inventory, and even payables	3.51	GE	3.28	GE	3.40	GE
5) Assessing the capital structure or net worth and the leverage of the borrower	3.63	GE	3.44	GE	3.54	GE
6) Evaluating the client's capability to control expenses to attain a higher income	3.26	GE	3.13	ME	3.20	ME
Factor Average	3.60	GE	3.42	GE	3.51	GE
1.00 – 1.75 Never (N)			1.76 – 2.50 Less Extent (LE)			
2.51 – 3.25 Moderate Extent (ME)			3.26 – 4.00 Great Extent (GE)			

The extent of implementation of credit practices in terms of collateral is shown in Table 4.

Table 4

The Extent of Implementation of Credit Practices in terms of Collateral

as compared to other competitors	3.94	GE	2.97	ME	3.46	GE
3) Evaluating the competitive climate for the client's products or services	3.11	ME	2.99	ME	3.05	ME
4) Assessing the results of increasing prices of commodities that could affect borrowers' financial status	3.11	ME	3.01	ME	3.06	ME
5) Evaluating the job outlook or businesses by projecting the future for sustainable operations	3.23	ME	3.08	ME	3.16	ME
6) Observing the economic, social, and other factors that could potentially affect the borrower	3.09	ME	3.06	ME	3.08	ME
Factor Average	3.29	GE	3.04	ME	3.17	ME
1.00 – 1.75 Never (N)			1.76 – 2.50 Less Extent (LE)			
2.51 – 3.25 Moderate Extent (ME)			3.26 – 4.00 Great Extent (GE)			

The extent of implementation of credit practices in terms of control is shown in Table 6.

Table 6

The Extent of Implementation of Credit Practices in terms of Control

Indicators	Managerial Personnel n = 37		Rank and File Employees n = 73		Item Average	
	μ	Scale	μ	Scale	μ	Scale
1) Ascertaining the implementation of applicable corporate regulatory requirements of government authorities (i.e., SEC, BSP)	3.83	GE	3.68	GE	3.76	GE
2) Ensuring that adequate loan documentation will be done for review by internal or external auditors	3.89	GE	3.78	GE	3.84	GE
3) Preparing loan documents correctly to be properly signed by the borrower and its guarantors or co-makers	3.94	GE	3.90	GE	3.92	GE

4) Granting loan values or amounts based on the criteria and the company's written credit policies	3.94	GE	3.76	GE	3.85	GE
5) Considering the recommendations from experts, experienced officers, or consultants in formulating policies	3.20	ME	3.11	ME	3.16	ME
Factor Average	3.76	GE	3.65	GE	3.71	GE
1.00 – 1.75 Never (N)			1.76 – 2.50 Less Extent (LE)			
2.51 – 3.25 Moderate Extent (ME)			3.26 – 4.00 Great Extent (GE)			

The summary of the extent of implementation of credit practices in terms of control is shown in Table 7.

Table 7

The Summary of the Extent of Implementation of Credit Practices in terms of Control

Credit Practices In Terms of :	Managerial Personnel n=37		Rank and File Employees n =73		Factor Average	
	μ	Scale	μ	Scale	μ	Scale
Character	3.52	GE	3.35	GE	3.44	GE
Capacity	3.59	GE	3.48	GE	3.54	GE
Cash Flow	3.60	GE	3.42	GE	3.51	GE
Collateral	3.11	ME	3.13	ME	3.12	ME
Condition	3.29	GE	3.04	ME	3.17	ME
Control	3.76	GE	3.65	GE	3.71	GE

General Average	3.48	GE	3.35	GE	3.41	GE
1.00 – 1.75 Never (N)			1.76 – 2.50 Less Extent (LE)			
2.51 – 3.25 Moderate Extent (ME)			3.26 – 4.00 Great Extent (GE)			

The extent of implementation of collection practices in terms of documentation is shown in Table 8.

Table 8

The Extent of Implementation of Collection Practices in terms of Documentation

Indicators	Managerial Personnel n = 37		Rank and File Employees n = 73		Item Average	
	μ	Scale	μ	Scale	μ	Scale
1) Sending of reminder notices to clients on or before their respective due dates	3.16	ME	3.40	GE	3.28	GE
2) Sending of reminder letters through registered mails	3.19	ME	3.51	GE	3.35	GE
3) Sending at least three (3) collection or demand letters to all past due borrowers	3.46	GE	3.67	GE	3.57	GE
4) Incorporating the statement of accounts in the demand letter and specifying the details of the charges	3.35	GE	3.28	GE	3.32	GE
5) Requiring collectors to prepare a weekly and/or daily collection plans	3.51	GE	3.40	GE	3.46	GE
6) Requiring collectors to take down notes on every arrangements made	3.51	GE	3.44	GE	3.48	GE
7) Preparing collection plans and strategies for implementation by collection officers	3.57	GE	3.51	GE	3.54	GE
8) Monitoring the effectiveness of collection systems and strategies implemented	3.57	GE	3.49	GE	3.53	GE
9) Conducting and/or assisting in the conduct of performance evaluation of individual collectors	3.62	GE	3.49	GE	3.56	GE
Factor Average	3.44	GE	3.47	GE	3.46	GE
1.00 – 1.75 Never (N)			1.76 – 2.50 Less Extent (LE)			

2.51 – 3.25 Moderate Extent (ME)

3.26 – 4.00 Great Extent (GE)

The extent of implementation of collection practices in terms of manpower is shown in Table 9.

Table 9

The Extent of Implementation of Collection Practices in terms of Manpower

Indicators	Managerial Personnel n = 37		Rank and File Employees n = 73		Item Average	
	μ	Scale	μ	Scale	μ	Scale
1) Assigning specific personnel to prepare collection/demand letters	3.62	GE	3.54	GE	3.58	GE
2) Training collectors on effective collection techniques and strategies	3.75	GE	3.60	GE	3.68	GE
3) Requiring collectors to be knowledgeable on how to compute payables in front of borrowers	3.76	GE	3.74	GE	3.75	GE
4) Instructing collectors to advise borrowers on the best payment alternatives for the settlement of their past due accounts	3.78	GE	3.69	GE	3.74	GE
5) Requiring collectors to be aware on the status of all individual borrowers on their respective areas of responsibility	3.78	GE	3.64	GE	3.71	GE
6) Hiring of full time legal/or paralegal officer to handle all legal matters and concerns	3.50	GE	3.46	GE	3.48	GE
7) Maintaining a legal retainer or part-time legal services of a lawyer	3.30	GE	3.46	GE	3.38	GE
Factor Average	3.64	GE	3.59	GE	3.62	GE
1.00 – 1.75 Never (N)		1.76 – 2.50 Less Extent (LE)				
2.51 – 3.25 Moderate Extent (ME)		3.26 – 4.00 Great Extent (GE)				

The extent of implementation of collection practices in terms of procedures is shown in Table 10.

Table 10

The Extent of Implementation of Collection Practices in terms of Procedures

Indicators	Managerial Personnel n = 37		Rank and File Employees n = 73		Item Average	
	μ	Scale	μ	Scale	μ	Scale
1) Calling the attention of the borrowers who are delinquent on their scheduled amortizations	3.81	GE	3.58	GE	3.70	GE
2) Informing the borrowers that delinquency could result to penalties and additional charges	3.73	GE	3.66	GE	3.70	GE
3) Requesting the delinquent borrowers to update their payments	3.81	GE	3.71	GE	3.76	GE
4) Informing the borrowers on the financial charges (e.g., interest, penalties, and other charges) in case of past due obligation	3.81	GE	3.75	GE	3.78	GE
5) Providing motorcycle to collectors for mobility purposes	3.54	GE	3.32	GE	3.43	GE
6) Instructing collectors to make follow-ups on every commitment made by borrowers	3.68	GE	3.64	GE	3.66	GE
7) Giving of incentives and/or bonuses based on actual collection and past due accounts settled	2.95	ME	3.00	ME	2.98	ME
8) Requiring collectors to bring statement of accounts for presentation to borrowers	3.51	GE	3.47	GE	3.49	GE
9) Instructing collectors to collect or visit past due borrowers at least once a week and exhausting all possible means to contract all past due borrowers	3.30	GE	3.48	GE	3.39	GE
10) In case of salary automatic payroll deduction system, requiring collectors to make monthly follow-ups	3.24	ME	3.53	GE	3.39	GE
11) Setting up and organizing the works of the collection team	3.46	GE	3.51	GE	3.49	GE

12) Training and mentoring collectors or collection officers for effectiveness in the collection operations	3.59	GE	3.63	GE	3.61	GE
13) Making recommendations to higher level management for approval in the implementation of appropriate collection strategies	3.70	GE	3.51	GE	3.61	GE
14) Conducting and/or assisting in the conduct of negotiations of highly problematic and long period past due accounts	3.62	GE	3.61	GE	3.62	GE
15) Making appropriate calls after incurring 2 or 3 delinquencies in the scheduled amortizations	3.73	GE	3.71	GE	3.72	GE
16) Finding out the reasons or causes of delinquency or past due	3.68	GE	3.63	GE	3.66	GE
17) Making a follow up call on a continuous basis	3.59	GE	3.48	GE	3.54	GE
18) Setting up a fixed date when the payment will be made by the delinquent/past due borrower	3.62	GE	3.58	GE	3.60	GE
19) Questioning the borrower whether future payments will be done promptly	3.32	GE	3.38	GE	3.35	GE
20) Informing the delinquent/past due borrowers that the company may be able to provide guidance	3.47	GE	3.86	GE	3.67	GE
21) Requiring all borrowers to open a savings account in the bank and in the case of lending company, a Time Deposit with other banking institutions in the locality	3.00	ME	3.32	GE	3.16	ME
22) Assigning the deposit accounts and be considered as hold-out on deposits for offsetting purposes	2.73	ME	3.10	ME	2.92	ME
23) Considering hold-out on deposits as non-withdrawable by the borrower unless the loan is fully paid	2.78	ME	3.04	ME	2.91	ME
24) Providing conditions that in case of delinquency or non-payment of loan, the company can take the deposit for the settlement of obligations	2.84	ME	3.11	ME	2.98	ME

25) Stating explicitly in the loan papers and documents the charging off or the use of savings or time deposit to offset (i.e., be charged) in case of non-payment	2.95	ME	3.07	ME	3.01	ME
26) Requiring the borrowers to deposit/retain the savings passbook of the bank and in the case of lending company, the Certificate of Time Depsoit (CTD) from other banks with notarized authority to withdraw and be used only in case of non-payment of obligations	2.61	ME	3.15	ME	2.88	ME
27) Deciding to take legal action after exhausting all remedies to collect past due accounts	3.65	GE	3.57	GE	3.61	GE
28) Considering legal action when the accounts are already long overdue based on aging of accounts	3.54	GE	3.56	GE	3.55	GE
29) Resorting to legal action only when the account is highly problematic and the borrower has no intention to pay his obligation	3.54	GE	3.60	GE	3.57	GE
30) Availing the Small Claims Court when the account or loan value is One Hundred Thousand Pesos and below for case filing purposes	3.00	ME	3.03	ME	3.02	ME
31) Ascertaining whether the past due borrower has still the ability to pay (i.e., not insolvent) before any legal action be made to avoid unnecessary legal expenses	3.51	GE	3.54	GE	3.53	GE
Factor Average	3.40	GE	3.46	GE	3.43	GE
1.00 – 1.75 Never (N)			1.76 – 2.50 Less Extent (LE)			
2.51 – 3.25 Moderate Extent (ME)			3.26 – 4.00 Great Extent (GE)			

The summary of the extent of implementation of collection practices in terms of control is shown in Table 11.

Table 11

The Summary of the Extent of Implementation of Collection Practices in terms of Control

Collection Practices In Terms of :	Managerial Personnel n = 37		Rank and File Employees n = 73		Factor Average	
	μ	Scale	μ	Scale	μ	Scale
Documentation	3.44	GE	3.47	GE	3.46	GE
Manpower	3.64	GE	3.59	GE	3.62	GE
Procedure	3.40	GE	3.46	GE	3.43	GE
General Average	3.49	GE	3.51	GE	3.50	GE

1.00 – 1.75 Never (N)
2.51 – 3.25 Moderate Extent (ME)

1.76 – 2.50 Less Extent (LE)
3.26 – 4.00 Great Extent (GE)

The difference between the evaluation of the managerial personnel and the rank-and-file employees regarding the extent to which credit practices are implemented is shown in Table 12.

Table 12

The Difference Between the Evaluation of the Managerial Personnel and the Rank-and-File Employees in the Extent of Implementation of Credit Practices

Factors Compared	df	Critical t	Computed t	Decision	Interpretation
Character	16	2.120	1.049	Do Not Reject Ho	Not Significant
Capacity	14	2.145	0.910	Do Not Reject Ho	Not Significant
Cash Flow	10	2.228	0.017	Do Not Reject Ho	Not Significant
Collateral	8	2.306	0.013	Do Not Reject Ho	Not Significant
Condition	10	2.228	1.834	Do Not Reject Ho	Not Significant
Control	8	2.306	0.575	Do Not Reject Ho	Not Significant

All Factors	10	2.228	0.997	Do Not Reject Ho	Not Significant
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The difference between the evaluation of the managerial personnel and the rank-and-file employees regarding the extent to which collection practices are implemented is shown in Table 13.

Table 13
The Difference Between the Evaluation of the Managerial Personnel and the Rank-and-File Employees in the Extent of Implementation of Collection Practices

Factors Compared	df	Critical t	Computed t	Decision	Interpretation
Documentation	16	2.120	0.419	Do Not Reject Ho	Not Significant
Manpower	12	2.179	0.638	Do Not Reject Ho	Not Significant
Procedures	60	2.000	0.759	Do Not Reject Ho	Not Significant
All Factors	4	2.776	0.156	Do Not Reject Ho	Not Significant

The proposed intervention schemes is shown in Table 14.

Table 14
The Proposed Intervention Schemes

Propo sal No.	Reference	Activities with Descriptive Ratings of Moderate Extent (ME)	Proposed Intervention Schemes/ Corrective Actions	Person(s) Responsible	Time Frame	Budget
1	Table 2, Item 7	Gathering information on personal habits such as gambling, drinking, sex morals, church involvement, and civic activities	Conducting Credit Investigation and/or Background Investigation (CI/BI) or information gathering on personal habits of prospective borrowers	Account/ Loan Officer	Before the approval of loan	P50,000.00 per semester and taken from Operations budget of the savings bank.
2	Table 2, Item 8	Securing the payment record of the client from other financial institutions	Requesting other Financial Institutions (FIs) to provide the payment record for the intended borrowers	Branch Manager/ Supervisor	Before the approval of the loan	P15,000.00 per semester

3	Table 2, Item 9	Sending and retrieving CI/BI Form with other Financial Institutions	Requesting other FIs to fill-up CI/BI Form to reflect the loan status and history of borrower, if any	Branch Manager/ Supervisor	Before the approval of the loan	Covered by the above budget for other FIs
4	Table 3, Item 6	Requiring at least two (2) guarantors or co-makers especially for non-collateralized loans	Requiring at least two (2) co-makers to fill-up and sign Promissory Notes and other documents to settle the loan in case of non-payment of the principal borrower.	Account/ Loan Officer	Before the approval of the loan	No Expense
5	Table 4, Item 6	Evaluating the borrower's ability to control expenses to attain higher income	Requiring the client to submit the financial profile that would reflect the income and expenses of the borrower	Account/ Loan Officer	Before the approval of the loan	No Expense
6	Table 5, Item 1	Ascertaining ownership of assets most preferably real properties as a possible collateral	Requiring applicant to fill-up forms reflecting ownership of assets/real estate properties	Account/ Loan Officer	Before the approval of the loan	No Expense
7	Table 5, Item 2	Considering real estate properties as the primary requirement for collateral purposes	Considering the real properties as the primary collateral of the borrower with possible higher loan value based on capacity	Account/ Loan Officer	Before the approval of the loan	No Expense
8	Table 5, Item 3	Considering other means of collateral to include chattel mortgage, post-dated checks, and other form of security for the loan.	Requiring other forms of collateral such as chattel mortgage, postdated checks, etc. for borrowers having no real properties with lower loan values as compared to loan with Real Estate Mortgage (REM)	Account/ Loan Officer	Before the approval of the loan	No Expense
9	Table 5, Item 4	Noting and clarifying liens, encumbrances, and other form of restrictions before a real property will be accepted as collateral	Verifying land titles on possible encumbrances and other form of restrictions before real property be considered as collateral	Account/ Loan Officer	Before the approval of the loan	No Expense
10	Table 5, Item 5	Requiring Real Estate Mortgage	Requiring Real Properties to be	Account/ Loan Officer	Before the	No Expense

		(REM) for real properties to be considered as collateral	considered as collateral and the transaction of loan be annotated at the Register of Deeds (ROD)		approval of the loan	
11	Table 6, Item 1	Ascertaining the prospective borrower's present status in business	Requiring the submission of client's business profile that would reflect the borrower's present status in business	Account/ Loan Officer	Before the approval of the loan	No Expense
12	Table 6, Item 3	Evaluating the competitive climate for the client's products or services	Based on the Business Profile, evaluating the competitive climate for the client's products or services	Account/ Loan Officer	Before the approval of the loan	No Expense
13	Table 6, Item 4	Assessing the results of increasing prices of commodities that could affect borrowers' financial status	Requiring submission of Audited Financial Statements and assess the increasing prices of goods that could affect the paying capacity of borrowers	Account/ Loan Officer/ Bank Manager	Before the approval of the loan	No Expense
14	Table 6, Item 5	Evaluating the job outlook or businesses by projecting the future for sustainable operations	Based on the data gathered, evaluating the business or job outlook by making projections for sustainability	Account/Loan Officer/ Supervisor/ Manager	Before the approval of the loan	No Expense
15	Table 6, Item 6	Observing the economic, social, and other factors that could potentially affect the borrower	Observance on the local rules and regulations, more particularly on the aspects of economic, social, and other factors	Account/Loan Officer/ Supervisor/ Manager	Before the approval of the loan	No Expense
16	Table 7, Item 5	Considering the recommendations from experts, experienced officers, or consultants in formulating policies	Consultation with experts, experienced officers, and consultants in the formulation of policies and guidelines	Manager/ Credit Manager	Before the approval of the loan	No Expense
17	Table 11, Item 7	Giving of incentives and/or bonuses based on actual collection and past due accounts settled	Giving of quotas or targets for the Collection Officers and the granting of monetary incentives or bonuses based on collection performance	Top Management / Manager	Monthly/ quarterly/semesterly/depending on policy	P20,000.00 to P30,000.00 per semester

18	Table 11, Item 21	Requiring all borrowers to open a savings account in the bank and in the case of lending company, a Time Deposit with other banking institutions in the locality	Requiring all the borrowers to open a Savings Account or Time Deposit with the bank and be considered as "Hold-Out Deposit for loan offsetting purposes	Account/ Loan Officer	After loan approval , before the release of the loan	No Expense
19	Table 11, Item 22	Assigning the deposit accounts and be considered as hold-out on deposits for offsetting purposes	Requiring the borrower to surrender the deposit passbook/Certificate of Time Deposit as one of the requirements for Hold-out on Deposit system	Manager/ Credit Manager	After loan approval , before release of the loan	No Expense
20	Table 11, Item 23	Considering hold-out on deposits as non-withdrawable by the borrower unless the loan is fully paid	Explaining to the borrowers that Hold-Out on Deposit" is non-withdrawable unless the loan is fully paid	Manager/ Credit Manager	After loan approval , before release of the loan	No Expense
21	Table 11, Item 24	Providing conditions that in case of delinquency or non-payment of loan, the company can take the deposit for the settlement of obligations	Approving a bank policy that in case of delinquency or non-payment of loan, the bank can take the deposit for the settlement of loan or obligations.	Board of Directors	During Board Meeting	No Expense
22	Table 11, Item 25	Stating explicitly in the loan papers and documents the charging off or the use of savings or time deposit to offset (i.e., be charged) in case of non-payment	Providing terms and conditions in the loan documents stating explicitly that in case of delinquency or non-payment of loan, the bank can take the deposit or charge-off for the settlement of loan	Manager/ Credit Manager	During the printing of the Loan Forms/ documents	No Expense
23	Table 11, Item 26	Requiring the borrowers to deposit/retain the savings passbook or the Certificate of Time Deposit (CTD) with notarized authority to charged off and be used only in case of non-payment of obligations	Requiring the borrowers to retain their passbook/Certificate of Time Deposit (CTD) with notarized authority to charged-off in case of non-payment of obligations	Manager/ Credit Manager	After loan approval , before the release of the loan	No Expense

24	Table 11, Item 30	Availing the Small Claims Court when the account or loan value is One Hundred Thousand Pesos and below for case filing purposes.	Resorting to "Small Claims Court" for the recovery of long-term past due accounts especially when the amount (e.g., One Hundred Thousand Pesos) is under the coverage of such law or regulation	Manager/ Credit Manager	Dependi ng on the bank policy or upon approval by the Board of Director s	P36,000.00 per semester
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DISCUSSION

Table 1 contains data pertaining to the extent to which the Savings Banks implemented the desirable credit practices in terms of character. Character is one of the aspects of credit to determine the borrower's integrity and personal character. This pertains to the individual's personality traits, moral values, family background, social connections, and business relationships (Sison, 2004). Basically, the borrower's trustworthiness, credibility and personality are also being considered. This can be assessed through their work experiences, credit history, reputation, credentials, references, and transactions with other lenders. This matters most because banks want to lend money to borrowers who have the commitment to pay their obligations.

As indicated by the factor average of 3.44 considering the group averages of 3.52 from the Managerial Personnel and 3.35 from the rank and file employees, the Savings Banks implemented to a **Great Extent** on credit practices in terms of **Character** of prospective borrowers.

Specifically, attaining the highest rating was the practice of securing information and knowing the reputation of potential borrowers among social, business friends, associates and from other financial institutions was implemented to a Great Extent, as reflected by the item average of 3.82 considering the weighted mean of 3.86 from the Managerial Personnel and 3.78 from the rank and file employees.

On the other hand, garnering the lowest rating was implemented to a Moderate Extent for gathering information on personal habits such as gambling, drinking, church involvement and civic activities, as denoted by the item average of 2.82 in view of the weighted mean of 2.89 from the Managerial personnel and 2.74 from the rank and file employees.

As revealed in Items 1 to 6 resulted that such practices were implemented to a Great Extent, while Items 7 to 10 were only implemented to a Moderate Extent. The activities implemented "*most of the time*" included the gathering of information on personal habits, securing the payment record from financial institutions, and the sending or retrieving of CI/BI forms with other financial institutions such as banks and lending companies.

In summary, majority of the items were implemented all the time by the concerned banks and the remaining three (3) items were implemented to a Moderate Extent only since there were banks who failed to get personal information of prospective borrowers

and that their application and related forms failed to capture the payment record or their failure to secure the CI/BI forms from other financial institutions.

Table 2 contains data pertaining to the extent to which the Savings Banks implemented the desirable credit practices in terms of Capacity. Capacity concerns on the customer's characteristics and one of the determinant factors whether the borrower has the ability to pay his obligations when it falls due. This is basically determined by evaluating the means of generating revenues, the employment status, business connections and involvement, the capacity of the borrower to enter into contracts, and the possible support of other people to act as guarantors in a loan transaction.

As reflected by the factor average of 3.54 taking into account the group average of 3.59 from the Managerial personnel and 3.48 from the rank and file employees, the Savings Banks implemented to a Great Extent on credit practices in terms of Capacity.

More particularly, as indicated by the item average of 3.92 considering the weighted mean of 3.94 from the Managerial personnel and 3.89 from the rank and file employees, the savings banks implemented to a Great Extent and with the highest result was the determination of the sources of income of the prospective borrower.

As denoted by the item average of 3.05 taking into account the weighted mean of 3.03 from the Managerial personnel and 3.07 from the rank and file employees, the savings banks implemented to a Moderate Extent and attaining the lowest rating was on the requirement of at least two (2) guarantors or co-makers especially for non-collateralized loans.

As revealed by the averages of Items 1 to 5 and 7 to 8, the desirable practices were implemented to a Great Extent. However, only Item 6 was implemented to a Moderate Extent. Implied by these findings, that "all the time" the savings banks had implemented almost all of the above practices, while, "most of the time" the savings banks implemented the measure of requiring at least two (2) guarantors or co-makers especially for non-collateralized loans.

The reason behind for not implementing all the time the requirement of co-makers was that there were banks that executed Memorandum of Agreements (MOAs) to agencies that strictly implemented the Automatic Payroll Deduction (APD) scheme for salaried employees and they could assure almost one hundred percent collection rate of their operations.

Table 3 presents items regarding the extent to which the savings banks implemented the desirable credit practices considering Cash Flow. Dexter (2007) cites that cash flow refers to how much a person is putting down and how much he has in reserve. This has something to do with the person's ability to generate monthly income from various sources, the bank deposits generating income in the form of interest, and reserves funds that would enable him to settle his obligations on time.

As denoted by the factor average of 3.51 taking into account the group average of 3.60 from the Managerial personnel and 3.42 from the rank and file employees, desirable credit practices in terms of **cash flow** were implemented to a **Great Extent**.

Specifically, the implementation by the savings banks was perceived to be at a Great Extent with the highest rating in the table. The scheme considers the take home pay or the overall income of the individual borrower and the past earnings, dividends,

and sales record in the case of a business firm or entity, as indicated by the item average of 3.81 considering the weighted mean of 3.86 from the Managerial personnel and 3.76 from the rank and file employees.

And the lowest point was on the aspect of evaluating the client's capability to control expenses for the attainment of higher income, implemented to a Moderate Extent as revealed by the item average of 3.20 denoted by the weighted mean of 3.26 from the Managerial personnel which is considered implemented to a Great Extent and 3.13 from the rank and file employees viewed as implemented to a Moderate Extent.

In view of the above results, it could be concluded that "all the time", the savings banks had implemented Items 1 to 5. While for Item 6, they implemented the practice of evaluating the borrower's ability to control expenses to attain a higher income in "most of the time."

Conclusively, the Savings Banks had implemented all the time the best practices as enumerated in the above Table except the system of assessing the prospective client's ability to control expenses. This is due to the fact, that not all banks can really calculate the person's ability to control expenses. However, the measure can easily be calculated by considering the savings and investments of the individual as evidenced by his deposits and investment documents.

Table 4 contains data on the implementation of credit practices in terms of collateral of the Savings Banks. Collateral represents an asset that can be used to guarantee and secure for the payment of loans. Some assets can be categorized as hard collateral like real properties to include land and structures. This type of collateral is more acceptable as compared to other form security since land will not depreciate and can be foreclosed by the bank in case of non-payment of obligations.

As reflected by the factor average of 3.12 considering the group average of 3.11 from the Managerial personnel and 3.13 from the rank and file employees, the credit practice requiring collaterals were implemented to a Moderate Extent among the savings banks.

The highest indicator that was implemented and rated as Moderate Extent was the measure of considering real estate properties as the primary requirement for collateral purposes, as denoted by the item average of 3.23 (i.e., ME) based on the weighted mean of 3.14 (i.e., ME) from the Managerial personnel and 3.31 (i.e., GE) from the rank and file employees.

Further, another measure which was implemented to a Moderate Extent and considered the lowest in rating was requiring Real Estate Mortgage (REM) for real properties to be considered as collateral, as shown by the item average of 3.03 in view of the weighted mean of 3.09 from the Managerial personnel and 2.97 from the rank and file employees.

As a result, implemented to a Moderate Extent were the measures of all items in the above Table. *Thus, the findings revealed that "most of the time", the savings banks had implemented the above desirable practices.*

This was due to the reason that, not all banks require collaterals to their clients since the BSP also allows the granting of clean loans (i.e., no collaterals) to their borrowers. Thus, other banks also extended salary loans, micro-finance credit, and other

types of clean lines of credit since they can also generate more profits by the imposition of higher interest rates as compared to collateralized loans.

Table 5 presents data on the implementation of credit practices in terms of condition as implemented by the Savings Banks. Condition is concerned on the status of the individual and/or as a company as a potential client. It is focused on the situation of a person or his business, its competitiveness, financial standing, sustainability, and other economic conditions that enable the prospective borrower to promptly settle his or her obligations.

As reflected by the factor average of 3.17 considering the group average of 3.29 from the Managerial personnel and 3.04 from the rank and file employees, the implementation of credit practices in terms of condition were implemented in the Savings Banks to a **Moderate Extent**.

To a Great Extent and obtaining the highest rating, was the measure of determining the client's profession or business standing as compared to other competitors were undertaken by the savings banks as indicated by the item average of 3.46 taking into account the weighted mean of 3.94 from the Managerial personnel and 2.97 from the rank and file employees.

Implemented to a Moderate Extent that was rated as the lowest was the measure in evaluating the competitive climate for the client's products or services with an item average of 3.05 considering the weighted mean of 3.11 from the Managerial personnel and 2.99 from the rank and file employees as shown in the table.

Accordingly, as evaluated by the Managerial personnel and rank and file employees, only Item 2 was implemented to a Great Extent, while all the rest of the Items were implemented to a "Moderate Extent. In other words, these findings revealed that in Item 2, the savings banks had implemented "all the time" the determination of the client's performance as compared to other firms in the same industry. The remaining items, more particularly Items 1, and 3 to 6 were implemented "most of the time".

In conclusion, almost all the items of Table 6 were only implemented moderately. This was attributed to the reason that, the Savings Banks failed to fully implement the best practices in terms of ascertaining the best condition of the potential borrowers. Thus, the need for them to improve their practices on this aspect.

Table 6 presents data on the implementation of credit practices in terms of control as implemented by the Savings Banks. Control is one of the criteria for good credit practices. It also considers the external dimensions that could possibly affect the borrower's payment performance. The external aspect includes amendments of existing regulatory rules and policies that might affect the company or borrower such as: a) interest rates; b) the maximum loanable value that will be granted; c) tax increases that could possibly affect the revenues or income; and d) other possible revisions of existing government guidelines.

As revealed by the factor average of 3.71 considering the group average of 3.76 from the Managerial personnel and 3.65 from the rank and file employees, the implementation of credit practices in terms of condition were implemented in the Savings Banks to a **Great Extent**.

A measure which resulted to the implementation at a Great Extent and getting the highest rating concerns on preparing of loan documents correctly to be properly signed by the borrower and its guarantors or co-makers as reflected by the item average of 3.92 taking into account on the weighted mean of 3.94 from the Managerial personnel and 3.90 from the rank and file employees.

To a Moderate Extent, the savings banks implemented the strategy of considering the recommendations from experts, experienced officers, or consultants in formulating policies, as shown by the item average of 3.16 considering the weighted mean of 3.20 from the Managerial personnel and 3.11 from the rank and file employees and this was rated as the lowest among all indicators.

Consequently, as viewed by the two groups of respondents, Items 1 to 4 were implemented to a Great Extent, while Item 5 was implemented to a Moderate Extent. Thus, implied by this findings, the measure or practice of considering the recommendations from experts, experienced officers, or consultants in formulating policies was implemented “*most of the time.*” Then said items 1 to 4 were implemented “all the time” by the savings banks.

In summary, majority or almost all of the items were fully implemented by the banks except Item 5. The reason for non-full implementation of such item or measure was that such inputs were usually done by experts and not all banks availed the services of consultants since it can be expensive on the part of their respective institutions.

Table 7 portrays the summary of results on the credit practices of savings banks in the province of Cebu. As indicated by the **general average** of 3.41 taking into account the group general average of 3.48 from the Managerial personnel and 3.35 from the rank and file employees, measures of credit practices of savings banks were taken to a **Great Extent.**

Specifically, among the six dimensions of credit practices, there were two (2) dimensions in which measures were taken to a **Moderate Extent**, namely: Collateral and Condition. While, the four others were considered implemented to a **Great Extent** which include: Character, Capacity, Cash Flow, and Control. In other words, 4 Cs of Credit were implemented “*all the time*” and the above 2 Cs of Credit were only implemented “*most of the time*”.

As a result, the measures of collateral and condition were not fully implemented by the concerned banks due to the reason that not all loans granted to clients need collateral because of Products that does not need this requirement. Moreover, the ascertainment of condition of the prospective borrower were sometimes neglected giving more emphasis on the above-cted 4 Cs of Credit. Thus, the need for improvement.

As observed in the preceding Table, the ratings and the general averages for Managerial personnel as compared to the rank-and-file employees were higher. These were attributed to the fact that Managers were more aware of the overall implementation of their respective banks as compared to the rank-and-file employees.

Table 8 presents data regarding the extent of implementation of desirable collection practices of savings banks, more particularly on documentation. Documentation is all about recording, monitoring, requiring the appropriate customer’s profile, the signing of contract, and the actual recording of transactions. This is a tool to

monitor the borrowers performance in order to recover the funds released to the borrowers (Heaps, 2017).

As revealed by the factor average of 3.46 considering the group average of 3.44 from the Managerial personnel and 3.47 from the rank and file employees, the savings banks had implemented the collection practices in terms of documentation to a **Great Extent**.

Clearly, the practice of sending at least three (3) collection or demand letters to all past due borrowers was implemented to a **Great Extent** and obtained the highest score as indicated by the item average of 3.57 based on the weighted mean of 3.46 from the Managerial personnel and 3.67 from the rank and file employees.

While, the measure of sending reminder notices to clients on or before their respective due dates was also implemented to a **Great Extent**, but with a lowest rating as indicated by the item average of 3.28 based on the weighted mean of 3.16 from the Managerial personnel and 3.40 from the rank and file employees.

In summary, as revealed by the items 1 to 9, all the measures above were implemented "**all the time**" by the savings banks in Cebu.

It can be concluded that, all the concerned banking institutions had fully implemented the documentation standards or requirements of good lending operations. The above strategies were considered vital for the recovery of loans from clients.

Table 9 presents data regarding the extent to which the savings banks implemented strategies on Collection in terms of Manpower. Manpower is an indispensable requirement in the collection system because in the absence such personnel, the jobs and responsibilities could not be realized. They should effectively manage debt and collection procedures as part of a larger financial management function that is vital in ensuring the profitability and sustainability of operations. Manpower focuses on the credit managers, collectors, and other support officers or even retainers.

As denoted by the factor average of 3.62 based on the group weighted mean of 3.64 from the Managerial personnel and 3.59 from the rank and file employees, collection practices in terms of Manpower were adopted to a **Great Extent**.

Particularly, the measure of requiring collectors to be knowledgeable on how to compute payables in front of borrowers was implemented to a Great Extent with the highest rating as denoted by the item average of 3.75 considering the weighted mean of 3.76 from the Managerial personnel and 3.74 from the rank and file employees.

Also, as shown in the table, the practice of maintaining a legal retainer or part-time legal services of a lawyer was also implemented to a Great Extent attaining the lowest level as shown by the item average of 3.38 in view of the weighted average of 3.30 from the Managerial personnel and 3.46 from the rank and file employees was rated as the lowest.

From these findings, it could be inferred that, the savings bankshad implemented“all the time” Items 1 to 7 concerning collection practices in terms of manpower.

The results revealed that, the concerned banks had fully implemented the required structure and capability building of personnel to sustain a good performance in lending operations. That they realized the importance of Manpower as one of the factors that would contribute to the success of every business endeavor.

Table 10 presents the data on the extent to which the savings banks implemented the procedures of good collection systems. Procedure is the other strategy supplementing documentation and manpower to effectively carry out the functions of collection operations. The systems and strategies would comprise the use of telephone, the right to offset, and legal action.

As shown by the factor average of 3.43 based on the group average of 3.40 from the Managerial personnel and 3.46 from the rank and file employees, the procedures of collection were implemented to a **Great Extent** by the savings banks of Cebu.

Specifically, the measure of informing the borrowers on the financial charges (e.g., interest, penalties, and other charges) in case of past due obligation was implemented to a Great Extent obtaining the highest rating as reflected in the item average of 3.78 considering the weighted mean of 3.81 from the Managerial personnel and 3.75 from the rank and file employees.

While, the practice of requiring the borrowers to deposit/retain the savings passbook of the bank and in the case of a lending company, the Certificate of Time Deposit (CTD) from other banks with notarized authority to withdraw and be used only in case of non-payment of obligations was implemented to a Moderate Extent with the lowest rate as denoted by the item average of 2.88 considering the weighted mean of 2.61 from Managerial personnel and 3.15 from the rank and file employees was the lowest indicator.

The above findings showed that, the savings banks had implemented “ **all the time**” the measures specified on Items 1 to 6, 8 to 20, 27 to 29 and 31. Then, for Items 7, 21 to 26, and 30 were only implemented to a “**Moderate Extent or Most of the Time.**”

It was obvious that, majority of the items or procedures were fully implemented except for eight (8) items. The contents of such items would more or less covered the granting of incentives to collectors based on collection performance, the system of requiring borrowers to have “ Hold-out on Deposits” as one of the strategies to recover the loans granted in case of default, and the institution’s availment of the “Small Claims Court”.

The reasons behind the non-full implementation would comprised the following: a) that not all banks had realized that incentive could be one of the motivational factors for good performance; b) that other banks were not so familiar with the strategy of implementing the “Hold-Out-on Deposit” system; and c) other banks would more or less avoid implementing the strategy of bringing the collection efforts to the courts in order to avoid embarassment on the part of the borrowers and as much as possible avoid legal expenses.

Table 11 presents summarized data on collection practices of savings banks in Cebu. As indicated by the **general average** of 3.50 considering the **group general average** of 3.49 from the Managerial personnel and 3.51 from the rank and file employees, measures on collection practices of savings banks were taken to a **Great Extent**. Thus, all dimensions of collection practices were taken to a **Great Extent**.

The above findings revealed that, savings banks had implemented “**all the time**” the measures of documentation, manpower, and procedure.

Thus, considering the results in general, the Collection Practices comprising of documentation, manpower, and procedures were fully implemented by the concerned

banks. This was attributed to the fact, that majority of them through their policies had realized the need for serious implementation of good collection measures in order to have good collection performance.

Table 12 presents the results of the test of the hypothesis. As shown in the Table, **there are no significant differences** between the assessment of the **credit practices** implemented by the savings banks of the province of Cebu as revealed by the computed t value of 0.997 at .05 level of significance, which is less than 2.228, the region of rejection ten (10) degrees of freedom from all factors.

Specifically, **there were no significant differences** between the evaluation of the implementation of **credit practices in terms of character** measures in the savings banks, as denoted by the computed t- value of 1.049, which was less than 2.120, the region of rejection at 16 degrees of freedom.

This result could be gleaned in Table 1 that shows credit practices in terms of character were implemented to a **Great Extent** in the savings banks, according to the Managerial personnel and rank and file employees evaluation. This finding implied that as perceived by both groups, the savings banks were concerned, **all the time**, to consider **character** as one of the criteria in the granting of loans to clients.

There were no significant differences on the evaluation made by the Managerial personnel and the rank and file employees, on the implementation by the savings banks on **credit practices in terms of capacity**, as indicated by the computed t-value of 0.910, which was less than 2.145, the region of rejection at 14 degrees of freedom.

With reference to Table 2, it shows that as evaluated by both groups, credit practices in terms of capacity were implemented to a **Great Extent** in the savings banks of the province of Cebu. This finding implied that generally, practices which were intended to ascertain the borrowers' **capacity** were **implemented all the time**.

There are no significant differences between the Managerial personnel and the rank and file employees' evaluation of the implementation of **credit practices in terms cash flow** in the savings banks in the province of Cebu, as shown by the computed t-value of 0.017, which was less than 2.228, the region of rejection at 10 degrees of freedom.

This result could be gleaned from the data in Table 3, which revealed that according to the evaluation of the two groups, credit practices in terms of cash flow were implemented to a **Great Extent**. Implied by this finding was the fact that, **all the time**, the desired practices of considering the cash flow of the borrowers were implemented by the savings banks.

There were no significant differences between the Managerial personnel and the rank and file employees' evaluation of the **credit practices in terms of collateral** as implemented by the savings banks, as shown by the computed t-value of 0.013, which was less than 2.306, the region of rejection at eight (8) degrees of freedom.

With reference to Table 4, it shows that according to evaluation of the two groups, the credit practice of considering collateral were implemented to a **Moderate Extent**. From this finding, it could be inferred that, **most of the time**, such credit practice of considering collateral were required by the savings banks in order to secure the payment of borrower's obligations.

There were no significant differences between the Management personnel and the rank and file employees' evaluation of the **credit practices in terms of condition** as implemented by the savings banks, as denoted by the computed t-value of 1.834, which was less than 2.228, the region of rejection at ten (10) degrees of freedom. This result could be gleaned from Table 5, which showed that according to the evaluation of the two groups, credit practices in terms of condition were implemented to a **Moderate Extent**. Implied by this finding was the fact that the assessment of the borrower's condition were generally implemented by the savings banks in **most of the time**.

There were no significant differences in the Managerial personnel and the rank and file employees' evaluation of the implementation of **credit practices in terms of control**, as denoted by the computed t-value of 0.575, which was less than 2.306, the region of rejection at eight (8) degrees of freedom. Upon looking into Table 6, it shows that as evaluated by both groups, the credit practices of control were implemented to a **Great Extent**. This finding implied that generally, the practices intended to screen the borrowers on the criteria of control were implemented **all the time**.

In the context of the results of the T-Test, **the null hypothesis was Accepted**.

Table 13 presents the results of the test of the hypothesis. As revealed in the Table, there are no significant differences between the assessment of the **collection practices** implemented by the savings banks of the province of Cebu as shown by the computed t-value of 0.156 at .05 level of significance, which was less than 2.776, the region of rejection at four (4) degrees of freedom from all factors.

Specifically, **there were no significant differences** between the evaluation of the implementation of **collection practices in terms of documentation** in the savings banks, as denoted by the computed t-value of 0.419, which was less than 2.120, the region of rejection at 16 degrees of freedom.

This outcome could be gleaned in Table 8 which shows that collection practices in terms of documentation were implemented to a **Great Extent** in the savings banks, according to the Managerial personnel and rank and file employees' evaluation. This finding implied that as perceived by both groups, the savings banks were concerned, **all the time**, to consider **proper documentation** as one of the systems in the granting of loans.

There are no significant differences on the assessment made by the Managerial personnel and the rank and file employees, on the implementation by the savings banks on **collection practices in terms of manpower**, as revealed by the computed t-value of 0.638, which was less than 2.179, the region of rejection at 12 degrees of freedom.

Considering the results in Table 9, it shows that as evaluated by both groups, **collection practices in terms of manpower** are implemented to a **Great Extent** in the savings banks of the province of Cebu. This finding implied that generally, practices which were intended to consider the manpower needs and requirements were **implemented all the time**.

There are no significant differences between the Managerial personnel and the rank and file employees' evaluation of the implementation of **collection practices in terms procedure** in the savings banks in the province of Cebu, as indicated by the

computed t-value of 0.759, which was less than 2.000, the region of rejection at 60 degrees of freedom.

This outcome could be gleaned from the data in Table 10, which revealed that according to the evaluation of the two groups, collection practices in terms of procedure were implemented to a **Great Extent**. Implied by this finding was the fact that, **all the time**, the desired practices of considering the **procedures of loan collections** were implemented by the savings banks.

In the context of the results of the T-Test, **the null hypothesis was Accepted**.

Based on the results of Table 12 and Table 13 above, there are no significant differences on the perception of the managerial personnel as compared to the rank-and-file staff since they are all employees of their respective companies and that they received the same orientation and/or seminars on their programs, projects, and activities. In other words, they were all aware of the policies and the corresponding implementation of their banks, except those who are new employees.

Table 14 presents the proposal intervention schemes.

Proposal No. 1: Conducting Credit Investigation and/or Background Investigation (CI/BI) or information gathering on personal habits of prospective borrowers.

The savings bank should seriously require the Loan Officers to conduct proper credit and background checking of all prospective borrowers concerning their personal habits such as gambling, drinking, morals, church involvement, and other social and civic activities. The results of the CI/BI could be one of the basis for the approval of loans to the borrowers. Without the needed background investigation, the granting of loans would be haphazardly done and would likely result to delinquency in the payment of obligations.

Proposal No. 2: Requesting other Financial Institutions (Fis) to provide the payment record for the intended borrowers.

The savings bank through the Branch Manager shall send a letter-request to other financial institutions like other banks and lending companies to provide the payment performance of the potential borrower. The names of the potential borrowers will be specified in the letter for them to identify if such names are also their clients. The data provided by such institutions can greatly help the banks decide on the amount or for the approval or disapproval of the proposed loan. There are tendencies wherein a potential borrower has so many loans with other financial institutions making him incapacitated to pay all his obligations. If this happens, the loan granted by the bank would become problematic and potential of not being recovered.

Proposal No. 3: Requesting other Financial Institutions to fill-up CI/BI Form to reflect the loan status and history of the borrower, if any.

As part of the Manager's request to other Financial Institutions is to simply fill-up the CI/BI Form easy accomplishment of the data. The form will be attached to the letter-request. The CI/BI Form will more or less capture the data on the name of the borrower, the residential address, the amount of loan granted, date granted, the loan balance, and the status of the loan either as current status or delinquent or under the past due status.

Once the loan status of the client is delinquent or considered past due, the bank can conclude that the potential loan has the risk of not being collected and will undergo the same status when granted. A good borrower has a record of loan under a "current status".

Proposal No. 4: Requiring at least two (2) co-makers to fill-up and sign Promissory Notes and other related documents to settle the loan in case of non-payment of the principal borrower.

Majority of the Loan Forms of banking institutions provided the requirement of having at least two (2) co-makers in order to guarantee the payment of the loan. If the principal borrower cannot pay his obligation, the co-makers will assume the responsibility of paying the obligation. One of the forms that they have to fill-up is the form on Co-Makers Statement with terms and conditions wherein they will be liable in case of non-settlement of the borrower. Having co-makers for the granting of loans will give assurance and security on the part of the lender. This will help minimize the risk of non-collection. This is usually required for non-collateralized loans like salary loans for government and private employees. But, for loans collateralized by Land Title or Real Estate Mortgage (REM), the requirement of co-makers will no longer be necessary.

Proposal No. 5: Requiring the client to submit the financial profile that would reflect the income and expenses of the borrower.

The savings bank should require their prospective clients to submit data, more particularly their financial profile to reflect their monthly or yearly income and expenses. There are other financial institutions that capture the financial profile of their clients in the application forms. Thus, there is no need to comply a separate form intended for financial profile.

Financial profile is very important since the data will serve as means by which the loan officer could analyze the paying capacity of the borrower. Capacity is one of the factors to be considered for efficient collection of loan accounts, hence it is included in this study.

Proposal No. 6: Requiring the applicant to fill-up forms reflecting ownership of assets /real estate properties.

The savings bank should also require the applicant-borrower to fill-up forms reflecting the ownership of assets, be it personal or real properties. There are banks which do not seriously require their borrowers to provide data on ownership of assets. The reason behind this requirement is that the loan officers or managers will be able to make suggestions for the client to provide adequate collateral especially the Real Estate Mortgage (REM) to assure collection of accounts. Besides, in case of delinquency of loans, especially salary loans, the bank can advise to the delinquent client to provide collateral for the renewal of his loan and make it current.

Proposal No. 7: Considering the real properties as the primary collateral of the borrower with possible higher loan value based on capacity.

One of the requirements of a good credit is the requirement of collateral by the borrower. Once it is collateralized, then it can be classified as a "Secured Loan". Speaking of secured loan, it has a high probability of collection and be also considered as low risk although collateral is only one factor for a good lending operations. Worse comes to worst, if the loan will not be paid, the collateral can be foreclosed and eventually be sold out and the proceeds be used to settle the obligations of the borrower. In addition, loans secured by Real Properties through Real Estate Mortgage (REM) will have a higher loan value as compared to clean loans or loans without collateral.

Proposal No. 8: Requiring other forms of collateral such as Chattel Mortgage, Post-dated Checks, etc. for borrowers having no real properties with lower loan values as compared to loan with Real Estate Mortgage (REM).

In the absence of real properties to be considered as collateral, the bank could require Chattel Mortgage (CM) for Vehicles that will serve as an alternative collateral just to assure recovery of loans. Post-dated checks could also be required as a collateral in the absence of REM or Chattel Mortgage. This has been practiced also by other financial institutions that grant loans to their clients.

Proposal No. 9: Verifying land titles on possible encumbrances and other form of restrictions before real property be considered as collateral.

Once the savings banks would require real properties as collateral, they should ascertain whether the Land Title is free from any restrictions such as liens and encumbrances. In other words, the land title is considered as a “Clean Title”, that there is no pending obligations or whatsoever circumstances that would affect the claim of the bank in case of foreclosure of the collateral.

Proposal No. 10: Requiring Real Properties be considered as collateral and the transaction of loan be annotated at the Register of Deeds(ROD).

Savings banks should consider the Land Title as collateral and be subjected to Real Estate Mortgage (REM). In other words, the document entitled, “Real Estate Mortgage (REM)” must be prepared and notarized. In addition, the mortgage or the loan should be annotated at the back of the land title or the transaction will be registered with the concerned Register of Deeds (ROD). The annotation shall only be cancelled once the loan is fully paid and the bank will issue a document on the “Cancellation of Mortgage”.

Proposal No. 11: Requiring the submission of client’s business profile that would reflect the borrower’s present status in business.

The savings bank should require the borrower’s business profile for business loans or those with businesses in order to add value to their paying capacity. This would also include the submission of their Articles of Incorporation and By-Laws in case of corporations applying for loans. For sole proprietorships, their DTI registration, licenses, and business permits.

Proposal No. 12: Based on the Business Profile, evaluating the competitive climate for client’s products or services.

The savings bank should evaluate the competition in the industry. Does the business have adequate market share, quality products or services, and possess the competitive advantage over other competitors in that kind of business. Because of this, the requirement of Business Profile is a very important requirement for the granting of loans especially for business loans.

Proposal No. 13: Requiring the submission of Audited Financial Statements and assess the increasing prices of goods that could affect the paying capacity of the borrower.

The savings bank should require their applicant-borrowers either as an individual or sole proprietorship, partnership, and corporation to submit Audited Financial Statements (i.e. Statement of Operations, Statement of Financial Condition, etc.) to assess the increasing prices of goods that could possibly affect the paying capacity of the client. The submission is very necessary since such documents will be utilized for financial analysis as to their liquidity, profitability, and sustainability.

Proposal No. 14: Based on the data gathered, evaluating the business or job outlook by making projections for sustainability.

In the case of business loans of a borrower, the bank should evaluate and make projections as to the type of business whether such undertaking will survive considering some factors to include competition, government regulations, and market acceptance. The assessment should be done in order to avoid the granting of loans wherein collection efficiency could be affected.

Proposal No. 15: Observance of the local rules and regulations, more particularly on the aspects of economic, social, and other factors.

The bank should ascertain as to whether the applicant for commercial loan with a corresponding business entity has complied with the local rules and regulations to include business permits and licenses. In addition, an evaluation should also be done by the bank if such business establishment has complied with the requirements of the SEC, BIR, and other regulatory agencies.

Proposal No. 16: Consultation with experts, experienced officers, and consultants in the formulation of policies and guidelines.

The bank management should get the ideas and opinions of business experts, experienced officers, and consultants that will assist in the formulation of bank policies, rules, and guidelines that will be approved by the Board of Directors. There are banks that will even hire the services of business or management consultants to assure greater probability of success in business operations.

Proposal No. 17: Giving of quotas or targets for the Collection Officers and the granting of monetary incentives or bonuses based on collection performance.

Savings banks should implement the "Management By Objectives (MBO)" system whereby employees will be given quotas or targets for a certain period i.e., 6 months. The quota to personnel should be attainable, realistic, and measurable. Upon reaching the required period, the actual accomplishments and targets will be compared as the basis for the rating. Based on the rating, the incentive or bonus will be granted.

In the case of bank collection officers, they will be given a quota or targets of collection for the period of six(6) months. After that period, their targets versus accomplishments will be considered and whoever gets at least Very Satisfactory rating will be given incentives or bonuses. The granting of such benefits can motivate collection officers to do their best for the attainment of their individual quotas.

Proposal No. 18: Requiring all the borrowers to open a Savings Account or Time Deposit with the bank and be considered as "Hold-out Deposit" for loan offsetting purposes.

The bank should require all their borrowers to deposit to the bank either savings or time deposit with a minimum amount based on percentage e.g., 10% of the loan value and such deposit will be considered as "Hold-out on Deposit". The amount deposited will not be withdrawable unless the total loan avilment will be fully paid by the borrower. In case the borrower could not pay his obligation, such deposit will be used for payment purposes, thus, reduce the receivables of the bank. In addition, the bank could also generate deposits from their borrowers that could add to their liquidity. There are general types of services of banks to include deposits generation and the granting of loans. This "Hold-out Deposit" system is one of the strategies for deposits generation.

Proposal No. 19: Requiring the borrower to surrender the deposit passbook/Certificate of Time Deposit as one of the requirements for Hold-Out on Deposit system.

It should be a policy of the bank, under the “Hold-out on Deposit” system that the concerned borrowers must deposit their deposit instruments (i.e, passbook, Certificate of Time Deposit) to the bank so that no withdrawals or pretermination will be done during the period of loan. Such deposit instruments will be returned to the borrower upon full-payment of his obligation. Thus, he can already withdraw/preterminate the amount deposited as soon as he is cleared of his financial obligations.

Proposal No. 20: Explaining to the borrowers that “Hold-out on Deposit” is non-withdrawable unless the loan is fully paid.

Again, based on the above discussion, the bank should properly explain to the borrowers that their deposits under the “Hold-out on Deposit” is non-withdrawable unless the loan is fully settled. This should also be part of the policy of the bank and such terms and conditions be incorporated in one of the documents of loan availment.

Proposal No. 21: Approving a bank policy that in case of delinquency or non-payment of loan, the bank can take the deposit for the settlement of loan or obligations.

As part of the policy under “Hold-out on Deposit” that in case of non-payment of obligations of the borrower, the bank can take the deposit and be applied or considered as part of the payment of the loan. At least such deposit can also be a recourse of partial collection.

Proposal No. 22: Providing terms and conditions in the loan documents stating explicitly that in case of delinquency or non-payment of loan, the bank can take the deposit or charge-off for the settlement of loan.

The bank should incorporate the provision in the loan papers that in case of default in the payment of loan, the lending bank can take the deposit and the amount will be used as partial or full payment of the balance of loan.

Proposal No. 23: Requiring the borrowers to retain their passbook/Certificate of Time Deposit (CTD) with notarized authority to charge-off in case of non-payment of obligations.

The bank should require the borrowers to retain in the custody of the bank their deposit documents with an “Authority to Charge-Off” in case of failure to pay the obligation. The authorization that will be signed by the borrower must be duly notarized.

Proposal No. 24: Resorting to “Small Claims Court” for the recovery of long-term past due accounts especially when the amount (e.g., One Hundred Thousand Pesos) is under the coverage of such law or regulation.

The bank should consider the policy of resorting to the “Small Claims Court” especially for amount covered under such law in order to effect collection of long-term problematic accounts or loans. This strategy could also help recover loans and thereby reducing the number of past due accounts.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher concludes that although the selected savings banks in Cebu are successfully operating, yet, enhancement and improvement of their practices, more particularly on the credit systems and collection strategies are necessary in order to be more effective and sustainable in their lending operations. This result affirms the principles of **Rose and Hudgins (2005)** on the C's of Credit Analysis and **Tomas Quintin D. Andres** as cited by **Apolo (2003)** on Collection Practices.

Recommendations

In the context of the findings of the study, the researcher recommends the following suggestions:

Primary Recommendation

The proposed "*Intervention Schemes/Proposals*" be adopted for implementation by the Savings Banks in Cebu;

Secondary Recommendation

The researcher would like to recommend to the future researcher to conduct a study on the following:

1. Customer Service and Client Retention Strategies of Savings Banks in the Province of Cebu: Bases for a Development Program.
2. Cost Reduction Measures and Profitability Strategies of Savings Banks in the province of Cebu: Bases for Improvement.
3. Employees' Performance and Reward Systems of Savings Banks in the province of Cebu: Bases for Enhancement.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The author(s) have stated that they have no potential conflicts of interest regarding the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article. The authors accomplished this study in compliance with the research ethics protocol. Informed consent were given to the respondents before the research instrument was distributed. The data were treated with utmost confidentiality.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank the managerial personnel and rank-and-file employees of the selected savings banks as respondents of this study. The authors also express their gratitude to the anonymous reviewers and editors for their valuable feedback and assistance in improving this manuscript.

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